

Table 2. Reaction of TM8089 to major diseases.

Disease	Reaction ^a			
	TM8089	TKM9	ADT36	IR50
Blast				
Field screening	R	S	R	HS
Artificial screening	MR	S	R	S
Brown spot	MR	MR	-	R
Bacterial blight	MR	MR	-	S
Neck blast	0	^b	MR	MR
Sheath rot	MR	MR	MR	MR
Glume discoloration	MR	MR	MR	MR

^a By the Standard evaluation system for rice. ^b Not tested.

Space limitations prevent IRRN from publishing solely yield data and yield component data from routine germplasm screening trials. Publication is limited to manuscripts that provide either a) data and analysis beyond yield and yield components (e.g., multiple or unique resistances and tolerances, broad adaptability), or b) novel ways of interpreting yield and yield component data across seasons and sites.

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soils

Effect of soil texture on rice growth and yield

J. C. Sharma, A. P. Sharma, and R. P. Agarwal, HAU Regional Agricultural Research Station, Uchani, Karnal 132001, India

We compared growth and yield of PR106 in pots in three soils of different textures: clay loam, loam, and sandy loam. Physicochemical properties of soils (deter-

mined by procedures of Chopra and Kanwar) are given in Table 1.

Recommended nutrients were applied, standard management practices followed. Plant samples were collected at tillering and panicle initiation. Yield was measured at harvest and grain samples taken for chemical analysis. N was estimated by semi-micro Kjeldahl's method, P by the procedure of Koenig and Johnson, and K by flame photometer.

Root dry matter and grain yield were significantly higher in fine-textured clay loam than in loam or sandy loam soils (Table 2). Plants grown in sandy loam

soils showed poor root growth and gave lowest grain yield. The higher yield in clay loam soils can be attributed to their higher nutrient-supplying capacity (CEC 16.8). ■

Physiology and plant nutrition

Effect of cutting frequency on rice herbage yield

T. Kupkanchanakul, S. Roontun, and K. Kupkanchanakul, Huntra Rice Experiment Station, Ayutthaya 13000, Thailand

We studied the effect of leaf cutting frequency on herbage yield, grain yield, and production components of deepwater rice under natural field conditions in 1988 wet season. Eight cutting frequencies and no cutting were arranged in a randomized complete block design with four replications (see table).

PG56 was sown at 120 kg seeds/ha onto plowed soil 20 May 1988. Seedling emergence was measured at end of May. The maximum water level was about 110 cm on 7 Nov 1988.

Herbage was collected by cutting at the collar level of the last fully developed leaves. The last cutting (130 d after emergence) was about 55 d before flowering.

Cutting at late growth stages and cutting more times significantly increased herbage yield. The highest dry herbage yield (2 t/ha) was with 3 cuttings at 40, 70, and 100 d after emergence.

Table 1. Physicochemical characteristics of the experimental soils.

	Clay loam	Loam	Sandy loam
pH (1:2)	8.1	8.3	8.5
EC (dS/m)	0.32	0.28	0.30
Organic carbon (%)	0.31	0.29	0.26
<i>Available nutrients (kg/ha)</i>			
N	160	140	130
P	7	6	6.5
K	265	240	210
Zn (ppm)	0.51	0.55	0.53
Sand (%)	25	51	57
Silt (%)	35	27	28
Clay (%)	39	21	14
CEC meq/100 g	16.8	12.2	8.3

Table 2. Effect of soil texture on grain yield, root dry matter, and nutrient uptake by rice.

Soil type	Root dry matter (g/pot)		Grain yield (g/pot)	Nutrients removed (g/pot)		
	At tillering	At panicle initiation		N	P	K
Sandy loam	4.2	6.8	14.7	10.7	0.05	0.15
Loam	4.5	7.2	17.9	12.1	0.05	0.16
Clay loam	5.2	7.9	23.1	15.3	0.07	0.21
LSD (0.05)	0.2	0.3	1.6	1.3	0.01	0.02

Rice grain yield was not affected by herbage removal. Panicles/m² increased significantly but spikelets/panicle, plant height, and biomass yield decreased significantly with increased cuttings. Fertility and 1,000-grain weight were not affected.

The ability to increase rice herbage yield by increasing cutting for herbage without detrimental effect on grain yield could benefit animal production, especially in rice cultivars with long growth duration. ■

Effect of cutting treatments on herbage yield, grain yield, and production components of PG56. Huntra Rice Experiment Station, Ayutthaya, Thailand, 1988 wet season.

Treatment ^b	Herbage yield (t/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Spikelets (no./panicle)	Fertility (%)	1000-grain wt (g)	Height at maturity (cm)	Biomass yield (t/ha)		
Control (no cut)	-	2.5	124	d 100	a	90	27.41	223 a	14.5 a	
One cutting, 40 DE	0.5	d 2.6	149	c	96	ab	85	27.14	214 ab	12.8 bc
One cutting, 70 DE	1.2	c 2.6	152	c	89	abc	87	28.01	202 bc	12.6 bc
One cutting, 100 DE	1.2	c 2.4	151	c	90	abc	88	28.83	201 bc	13.2 ab
One cutting, 130 DE	1.2	c 2.4	151	c	82	bcd	86	27.86	201 bc	13.0 bc
Two cuttings, 40+70 DE	1.4	bc 2.5	178	ab	75	cd	89	28.52	197 c	12.3 bc
Two cuttings, 40+100 DE	1.6	b 2.3	174	ab	72	cd	89	28.43	200 bc	12.3 bc
Two cuttings, 70+100 DE	1.9	a 2.3	162	bc	72	cd	85	28.11	194 c	11.5 c
Three cuttings, 40+70+100 DE	2.0	a 2.4	185	a	64	d	84	28.23	193 c	11.6 c

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bDE = days after emergence.

Fertilizer management

Effect on rice of placement depth of urea supergranules

A. Sen and E. K. Pandey, Agronomy Department, Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi 221005, U.P., India

We evaluated the effects of placement of urea supergranules (USG) (5, 10, and 15 cm deep and broadcast prilled urea (PU) on rice yields of tall, long-duration Mahsuri and dwarf, short-duration Madhuri.

The trial was laid out in a split-plot design with four replications during 1987 rainy season.

Soil was an Entisol-Tropofluent, alluvial, deep and flat. It was clay loam with 52.50% sand, 24.75% silt, and 22.75% clay; moderately fertile with 324.80-26.34-174.24 kg available NPK; pH 7.0; and CEC 25 meq/100 g soil.

Plant spacing was 15 × 20 cm. N was applied at 38.32 kg/ha.

One 1-g granule of USG was deep-placed in the middle of each four hills in alternate rows; prilled urea was broadcast in three splits at sowing, maximum tillering, and panicle initiation in a 1:2:1 ratio.

N conversion efficiency (NCE) was computed as

$$\text{Nitrogen conversion efficiency} = \frac{\text{Yield for USG placement} - \text{yield for PU}}{\text{N applied (38.32 kg/ha)}} \times 100$$

Mahsuri had significantly higher yield than Madhuri, although some lodging occurred during late growth (Table 1). Mahsuri produced significantly higher panicles/m², panicle length and weight, filled spikelets/panicle, and 1,000-grain weight. The yield difference was probably due to Mahsuri's long duration, about 1 mo longer than Madhuri.

All depths of USG placement resulted in higher yield characters than broadcast PU; however, differences except for panicle length were not significant. The

cumulative effect resulted in significantly higher grain and straw yield with USG.

Placement depth did not affect yields. Probably the fine soil texture ensured uniform availability of N to roots at all depths, with higher cation exchange capacity and less leaching loss.

In N conversion efficiency, 10 cm placement of USG was most efficient in Mahsuri, and 15 cm placement in Madhuri (Table 2). ■

Table 2. Nitrogen conversion efficiency for USG.

Placement depth (cm)	N efficiency (%)	
	Mahsuri	Madhuri
5	7.0	18.1
10	18.4	8.7
15	2.6	19.1

Table 1. Effect of USG and prilled urea on characters and yield of rice.

Treatment	Panicle (no./m ²)	Panicle length (cm)	Panicle weight (g)	Unfilled panicles (no.)	Filled spikelets (no./panicle)	1000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)
Mahsuri	354	23	43	21	306	21	2.3	4.1
Madhuri	247	21	20	34	110	15	1.6	2.4
LSD ^a	64	1.4**	11**	ns	149**	3**	0.6*	1.8**
USG depth								
5 cm	319	23	32	24	218	10	2.1	3.4
10 cm	326	22	32	23	222	18	2.1	3.6
15 cm	290	23	31	29	206	18	2.0	3.3
PU broadcast	267	20	30	33	186	18	1.6	2.7
LSD ^a	ns	1	ns	ns	ns	ns	0.4**	0.7**

^aSignificant at 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels. NS = nonsignificant.

Fertilizer management – inorganic sources

Integrated phosphorus management in a rice-based cropping system

L. Sreekantan and SP. Palaniappan, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, South India

We studied the effects of P management in a rice - rice - green gram cropping system. In first rice crop (variety IR50) Jun-Oct 1985, P at the recommended 22 kg P/ha was applied as superphosphate and rock phosphate, and no P alone and with 12 t/ha sunn hemp *Crotalaria*